

China and India as Space Powers: Geopolitics, Domestic Interests, and Prestige*

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Abstract

This paper employs an eclectic analytical framework, incorporating structural, domestic, and normative perspectives to assess the drivers behind China and India's space programs. While security concerns, particularly China's competition with the U.S. and India's response to China, are significant in explaining military space ambitions, domestic political dynamics and bureaucratic interests also play a critical role in shaping space policy decisions. Moreover, space accomplishments serve as sources of national prestige, political legitimacy, and international standing.

Keywords:

China, India, space, technonationalism, prestige

1. Introduction

Any discussion of contemporary space security has to pay particular attention to the role of China and India as space powers. It is not difficult to see why. China has been expanding its space capabilities in a systematic manner over the past two decades or so, emerging as a key player in civilian space activities. Indicative of its ambition to position itself as a global space power, China's achievements include a series of human spaceflight missions, a vigorous lunar space program, the completion of the *Tiangong* space station, and the deployment of the *Beidou* satellite navigation system, which provides Beijing with an independent global positioning capability. Alongside this, as discussed below, space has become increasingly central to China's military modernization, reflecting broader strategic goals and the growing importance of space-based assets for national security.

While China's emergence as a major space power has been widely recognized, India has also made substantial strides in space in recent years in both civilian and military space capabilities. Despite the fact that India has traditionally emphasized the use of space for socio-economic development, its space program has increasingly focused on prestige projects, achieving significant milestones in space exploration. At the same time, like China, India has been gradually integrating space into its broader national security, demonstrating a growing awareness of the military and geopolitical significance of space.

In light of the above, the aim of this short essay is to provide a brief overview of China and India as space powers. It begins by examining China's space program, outlining its major civilian achievements before briefly considering how China utilizes space for military purposes. The discussion then shifts to India, first highlighting its civilian space advancements and then offering a succinct review of how space has increasingly been integrated into national security. In lieu of a conclusion, the final section briefly examines the key drivers of China and India's space programs through the prism of an analytical eclectic approach, integrating insights from structural, domestic, and normative perspectives to provide a more comprehensive understanding of their strategic, political, and technological motivations.

2. China: A major power in space

China's recent remarkable achievements in space mean that one may be forgiven for thinking that its space program is a relatively new endeavor.¹ And yet, China has one of the world's longest-running space programs, with origins dating back to the mid-20th century, driven by a combination of national prestige and strategic considerations echoing the United States and the Soviet Union. Indeed, as Handberg and Li note "the reality of the Chinese space program was that their effort grew out of that same sense of military necessity along with the clear ancillary value of fostering China's international political prestige in a manner" that "clearly mirrored those of the United States and Soviet Union."² In this respect, a few useful observations are worth making from the outset. First, underpinning China's space endeavor from its inception was its close ties with the country's strategic weapons program. This connection became evident with the establishment of the Fifth Academy of the Department of Defense in 1956, led by the renowned scientist Qian Xuesen. As a missile research and development center, the academy played a crucial role in laying the groundwork for China's space ambitions.³

Second, the launch of Sputnik in 1957 was a pivotal moment that spurred China's interest in space. The Soviet achievement left a strong impression on Mao Zedong, who frequently referenced it in his speeches. At the Second Plenary Meeting of the Eighth Party Congress in May 1958, the Chinese premier famously announced, "We too should produce satellites," but insisted that China aim high: "If we're going to launch one, it should be at least two tons—not a small one like the Americans' chicken egg!"⁴

Mao's interest led to a push for the development of a Chinese satellite. But China's space ambitions were initially stalled by a combination of domestic political upheavals, including the Great Leap Forward and the Cultural Revolution, and the withdrawal of Soviet technical assistance for its missile program following the Sino-Soviet split. Even so, the Chinese leadership acknowledged the significance of the missile and space programs. Consequently, it sought to protect the engineers and scientists working in these fields from the political instability that disrupted other aspects of policymaking and society at large. These efforts bore fruit when, on April 24, 1970, China successfully launched its first satellite, Dong Fang Hong 1 (The East is Red), becoming the fifth country to place a satellite in orbit.⁵

China's early space ambitions were not limited to satellites. The successful launch of Dong Fang Hong 1 was made possible by the Long March 1 rocket, part of a broader effort to develop an indigenous launch capability. Around the same time, the Chinese leadership also initiated the early phases of a human spaceflight program, but Mao eventually decided to cancel it. Nevertheless, this brief interest in human spaceflight underscores the country's long-term commitment to establishing itself as a major space power.

What merits emphasis for the purposes of this discussion is that the space program's synergies with the strategic weapons program continued apace in the 1960s and 1970s. In fact, the launch of the first Chinese satellite was part of what is known in China as the "Two Bombs, One Satellite" or *Liangdan Yixing* (两弹一星) project. "Two Bombs" refers to the development of both the atomic and hydrogen bombs, along with intercontinental ballistic missiles (ICBMs), while "One Satellite" denotes the advancement satellite technology. Embodying China's integrated approach to national defense and technological self-reliance, the *Two Bombs, One Satellite* project highlights a techno-nationalist approach to strategic technologies that remains influential today.⁶

Deng Xiaoping reoriented China's space program toward economic development, emphasizing practical applications such as satellite communications.⁷ However, in 1986, an important effort was made to reassert a techno-nationalist approach to advanced technological development, drawing inspiration from the *Two Bombs, One Satellite* project. Initiated by four prominent scientists, this push resulted in the launch of the 863 High-Technology Research and

Development Plan, commonly known as the 863 Program. Its primary objective was to drive innovation and enhance China's technological capabilities in critical fields, including space.⁸ This, in turn, led the 863 Program to reignite interest in China's space efforts, culminating in the launch of its human spaceflight program in the early 1990s.⁹

Progressing from this basis, China has since pursued its space program with consistency and a gradual, methodical approach. Over time, it has developed across the board space capabilities enabling a wide range of applications. Not surprisingly, China's remarkable feats in human spaceflight and space exploration have attracted much global attention, solidifying its position as a leading space power. Apart from a rigorous human spaceflight and space exploration program, China has also made significant strides in satellite and rocket technology. China has developed an extensive array of satellites for communications, remote sensing, and navigation, with the *Beidou* satellite system standing out as a major milestone. More recently, it has shown a growing interest in the development of satellite megaconstellations, aiming to establish its own large-scale network for global broadband coverage, akin to Starlink.¹⁰ As far as rocket development is concerned, China has made significant progress in advancing its launch capabilities. The Long March rocket family has undergone continuous upgrades, enabling the deployment of satellites, crewed missions, and deep-space probes.¹¹ Furthermore, there has been an effort to step up the commercialization and privatization of its space sector, fostering the growth of private enterprises involved in satellite manufacturing, launch services, and space-based applications.¹²

Beyond technological advancements, it should be noted that China has also leveraged its space capabilities as a tool of foreign policy, particularly in its engagement with the Global South. For example, in 2008, it established the Asia-Pacific Space Cooperation Organization (APSCO) to promote collaboration among member states through training, data sharing, and capacity building in space technology.¹³ Similarly, it has integrated space activities into the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) through the Space Information Corridor or Space Silk Road.¹⁴ Equally, China attempts to bolster its image as a great power in space through initiatives such as the United Nations/China Cooperation on the Utilization of the China Space Station, which offers international scientists the opportunity to conduct experiments aboard its space station, enhancing its soft power.¹⁵ Likewise, the International Lunar Research Station (ILRS), launched in partnership with Russia's Roscosmos in 2021, is a planned lunar base for scientific research and exploration.¹⁶ Unlike China's UN-backed space initiatives, however, it is notable that the ILRS follows a bilateral framework but remains open to international participation.¹⁷ The point to make is here is that these initiatives reflect Beijing's effort to demonstrate its commitment to assuming great power responsibilities through the provision of public goods, though with certain limitations.¹⁸

2.1 China and Military Space

Symptomatic of its growing space activities, its expanding interests across the globe, and its wider military modernization, China has intensified its focus on the military uses of space. The increasing role of space technology in modern warfare after the Cold War drew significant attention from Chinese strategists, particularly following the 1991 Gulf War, often called the first space war. This conflict demonstrated how space assets could enhance both strategic and tactical military operations, prompting China to reassess its military doctrine and training. In 1993, under Jiang Zemin's leadership, China introduced the concept of "local wars under modern high-tech conditions," signaling a shift from industrial-age warfare to modern, technology-driven military capabilities. This modernization drive prioritized research and development in space-based technologies, including satellites, early warning systems, command networks, and advanced communication infrastructure. This process accelerated

with the emergence of the Revolution in Military Affairs, alongside other external developments, such as the transition to information warfare, the Kosovo War, and U.S.-led interventions in Afghanistan and Iraq, which reinforced the critical role of technology in contemporary warfare. By 2002, the strategic guidelines adopted the term “local wars under modern informationalized conditions,” emphasizing the growing nexus between information technology and military operations.¹⁹

Since Xi Jinping took power in 2012, interest in the military uses of space has gained significant momentum. In 2014, Xi urged the PLA Air Force to “speed up air and space integration and sharpen their offensive and defensive capabilities”. China’s 2015 defense white paper reinforced this priority, describing outer space as a “commanding height in international strategic competition.” Similarly, China’s most recent defense white paper, released in 2019, highlights “China’s security interests in outer space” as a key “national defense aim” and affirms that “[o]uter space is a critical domain in international strategic competition”.²⁰

This growing focus on military space aligns with Xi’s broader push for military modernization, which prioritizes transforming the PLA into a world-class military by mid-century. A central aspect of China’s military transformation is the policy of military-civil fusion (MCF), aimed at integrating civilian technological advancements into military applications to enhance China’s defense capabilities. Moreover, PLA reforms under Xi have sought to streamline operations across key domains.²¹ In 2015, China established the PLA Strategic Support Force (PLASSF) to centralize space, cyber, and electromagnetic operations. However, in a major restructuring announced in April 2024, the PLASSF was disbanded and replaced with new military units, including an Aerospace Force.²² While the full implications of this restructuring remain unclear, it reflects the growing importance of space assets under informationized warfare and the need for greater coordination in joint military operations across multiple domains.

This shift in military organization and doctrine has been accompanied by China’s growing investment in counterspace capabilities. The most visible demonstration of this was the 2007 direct-ascent anti-satellite (ASAT) test, which destroyed a defunct weather satellite, making China the third country to conduct such a test. The resulting debris, estimated at over 3,000 pieces, sparked international condemnation and raised concerns over China’s stance on space security. While China has since refrained from further debris-generating ASAT tests, it has continued developing non-destructive direct-ascent ASAT systems, including a 2013 test that reached approximately 30,000 km, suggesting the ability to target satellites in medium Earth orbit or higher. Aside direct-ascent ASATs, China is believed to be advancing a range of counterspace technologies, including co-orbital systems, directed energy weapons, and electronic warfare capabilities, all aimed at disrupting or neutralizing adversary space assets.²³

Concurrently, space has become integral to the PLA’s ability to conduct operations far beyond continental China, reflecting its expanding strategic reach. Traditionally focused on internal security and defense of the mainland, the PLA has increasingly prioritized long-distance missions, with space-based assets playing a key role as a force multiplier. In this context, a major focus has been enhancing command, control, communications, intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance (C4ISR) capabilities through an extensive network of both dedicated military and dual-use satellites. This includes communication satellites, high-resolution remote sensing satellites such as the *Yaogan*, *Haiyang*, *Huanjing*, and *Gaofen* series, as well as Tracking and Data Relay Satellites (TDRS) and the *Beidou* navigation system. Estimates suggest that nearly half of China’s satellite launches since 1970 have served military functions.²⁴ Alongside its 300 surveillance satellites in low Earth orbit, China has also expanded its geostationary orbit (GEO) surveillance capabilities with dual-use satellites like *Yaogan-41* and *Ludi Tance-4*, which enhance continuous monitoring over Taiwan and the Indo-Pacific, complicating U.S. and allied military operations in the region.²⁵

3. India: A Rising Space Power

Like China, India's space program is one of the oldest, with its origins tracing back to the early 1960s.²⁶ However, some scholars trace its foundations even earlier, linking it to India's participation in the International Geophysical Year (IGY) of 1957–1958, a global scientific initiative that contributed to the emergence of the Space Age with the launch of Sputnik 1 in 1957.²⁷ Notably, Vikram Sarabhai, often regarded as the father of India's space program, played an important role in these early efforts, which helped lay the foundation for India's later advancements in space technology. This led to the establishment of the Indian National Committee for Space Research (INCOSPAR) in 1962 and the launch of the first Nike-Apache sounding rocket from the Thumba Equatorial Rocket Launching Station (TERLS) in 1963, followed by the creation of the Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO) in 1969.

Unlike other space powers that heavily relied on military programs, however, India's space and missile development efforts remained distinct, with minimal technological overlap. Indian scientists prioritized practical applications deriving from space-based assets aligning with Sarabhai's vision of utilizing space for socio-economic development. In this respect, India's space program evolved around three key pillars: communications and remote-sensing satellites, practical applications, and space transportation systems.²⁸ In particular, the Indian National Satellite System (INSAT), operational since 1983, and the Indian Remote Sensing (IRS) satellite program, launched in 1988, supported vital functions such as meteorology, disaster monitoring, and resource management. Simultaneously, India established its own launch capabilities, starting with the Satellite Launch Vehicle (SLV)-3 in 1980 and later advancing to more sophisticated systems such as the Augmented Satellite Launch Vehicle (ASLV), the Polar Satellite Launch Vehicle (PSLV), and the Geosynchronous Satellite Launch Vehicle (GSLV).²⁹

Although socio-economic priorities remain central, in recent years, India's space ambitions have broadened to encompass exploration and strategic objectives, reflecting its aspirations for great power status, its growing economic clout, and an increasingly challenging security environment.³⁰ The launch of Chandrayaan-1 in 2008, which confirmed the presence of water molecules on the Moon, signaled this shift. It was followed by the Mars Orbiter Mission (Mangalyaan) in 2013, making India the first Asian nation to reach Mars, a milestone some analysts viewed as strategically motivated in light of China's space advancements. In 2018, Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced India's first human spaceflight mission, *Gaganyaan*. As part of its long-term ambitions, India has also outlined plans to establish its own independent space station by 2035, further solidifying its position as a major space power. As well, India has increasingly promoted commercialization and privatization in its space sector.

Importantly, as part of this reorientation of Indian space policy, New Delhi has become more willing to use space technology as a foreign policy tool, partly in response to China's growing influence in South Asia. A key example has been Modi's 2014 proposal for a South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) satellite, aimed at enhancing regional connectivity. Renamed the South Asia Satellite after Pakistan withdrew, it was successfully launched in May 2017, providing disaster management support, telemedicine, tele-education, and weather forecasting services to Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Nepal, the Maldives, and Sri Lanka.³¹

3.1 India and military space

While these advancements serve to highlight India's expanding civilian space capabilities, its space program has also taken on an increasingly strategic dimension. This has been

manifested in the deployment of satellites that enhance India's defense capabilities.³² Since 2000, ISRO has launched several dual-use Earth observation satellites capable of providing high-resolution imagery with military applications. The 1999 Kargil War exposed weaknesses in India's surveillance infrastructure, leading to greater investment in space-based reconnaissance.³³ Some satellites in the IRS series are believed to have military utility, while the CARTOSAT series delivers high-resolution data. Furthermore, the RISAT (Radar Imaging Satellite) series, equipped with synthetic aperture radar (SAR) enable Earth observation for dual-use purposes. India has also established NavIC (Navigation with Indian Constellation), an independent regional navigation system providing positioning, navigation, and timing (PNT) services. While its Standard Position Service (SPS) is open to civilian users, the Restricted Service (RS) is encrypted for military operations. ISRO has also collaborated with the Airport Authority of India (AAI) to develop GAGAN (GPS Aided Geo Augmented Navigation), which has potential dual-use utility.

Apart from these dual-use capabilities, India has also prioritized the development of dedicated military space assets to strengthen its defense posture in space. In 2013, ISRO launched GSAT-7, India's first military communications satellite, enhancing the Indian Navy's maritime surveillance and operational capabilities. This was followed by GSAT-7A in 2018, designed to improve communication for the Indian Air Force. In 2019, India launched EMISAT, an electronic intelligence (ELINT) satellite jointly developed by ISRO and the Defence Research and Development Organisation (DRDO), aimed at detecting and intercepting hostile radar signals.³⁴

But India's growing focus on military space capabilities has not been limited to satellites. A significant demonstration of the shift toward the use of space for national security came with Mission Shakti, in which a missile launched from the Kalam Island missile complex successfully intercepted the Microsat-R satellite, which was developed by the Defence Research and Development Organisation (DRDO) and launched by ISRO in January 2019, in low Earth orbit at approximately 300 km. The destruction of Microsat-R marked a major milestone in India's military space program. With this test, India became the fourth country, after the United States, Russia, and China, to demonstrate ASAT capabilities, signaling its intent to strengthen its counterspace capabilities.³⁵

To further integrate space into military operations, India established the Integrated Space Cell in 2010 under the Integrated Defence Services (IDS) Headquarters to coordinate the use of space assets across the three branches of the armed forces, ISRO, and the Department of Space. Following the 2019 ASAT test, India reinforced this by creating the Defence Space Agency (DSA) to address space-based threats and expand its defense capabilities. Together with this, the government approved the Defence Space Research Organisation (DSRO) to support space warfare development and provide technical expertise to the DSA. To complement these efforts, ISRO initiated Project NETRA (Network for Space Objects, Tracking, and Analysis), a space situational awareness system designed to monitor space objects and provide early warnings of potential threats, further securing India's space assets. In tandem with improving its independent military space capabilities, India has deepened strategic space partnerships, particularly with the United States, to counter China. Another example is the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad), comprising Australia, India, Japan, and the United States, which has expanded its focus to space.³⁶

4. In lieu of a conclusion: Making sense of China and India as space powers

The rise of China and India as space powers cannot be understood through a single International Relations theoretical lens.³⁷ Instead, an eclectic approach integrating structural imperatives, domestic politics, and normative considerations provides a more comprehensive understanding

of their space programs.³⁸ A focus on structural factors and systemic pressures associated with a realist-oriented approach offers a compelling explanation for both countries' pursuit of military space capabilities, including anti-satellite ASAT weapons. China's 2007 ASAT test was largely seen as a response to US military space dominance. Similarly, India's 2019 ASAT test reflected its strategic concerns about China's growing space power. The action-reaction dynamic between these states suggests a security dilemma in space, where one country's advancements prompt others to develop similar capabilities. However, while such concerns explain why China and India pursue military space capabilities, they do not fully account for the timing of key decisions and the rationales behind specific projects, including ASAT tests.

Looking at the impact of domestic political consideration helps bridge this gap, highlighting how internal bureaucratic and political factors shape space policies. In China's case, the 2007 ASAT test may have been driven by project managers seeking to demonstrate technological maturity and secure political approval for the program. Similarly, India's ASAT test was not solely about deterring China but also had strong domestic political motivations. The Modi government's decision to authorize the test despite the technology being available since 2012 coincided with the 2019 general elections, leading to accusations that it was exploited for electoral gain. Further reflecting domestic political considerations, space projects in China are tightly woven into state narratives, boosting national pride as well as the legitimacy of the Chinese Communist Party. Similarly, for political leaders like Modi, space achievements can serve as a means to bolster their personal image by associating their leadership with national strength and technological success.

Beside structural imperatives and domestic politics, taking into consideration the role of history and identity provides further insights into the motivations behind China and India's space ambitions. Both countries have sought to leverage space capabilities for great power status and prestige, using high-profile space achievements to signal their emergence as great powers. The 19th-century idea of scientific and technological progress as a "standard of civilization" reinforced a hierarchical view that distinguished European from non-European societies, influencing China and India, which continue to use space projects as symbols of power, status, and modernity, driven by an influential techno-nationalist ideology.³⁹

Therefore, China and India's space programs reflect a complex interplay of strategic, political, and identity-driven factors. While national security concerns have played a role, their pursuit of space capabilities, including ASATs, cannot be understood solely through a military lens. Domestic political considerations, bureaucratic interests, and leadership ambitions have shaped key decisions, while space achievements serve as symbols of national pride, political legitimacy, and great power status. An eclectic approach is essential to fully grasp the motivations behind their space programs, showing that space power is not just about power politics but also about prestige, domestic legitimacy, and broader aspirations for recognition in the ensuing global space order.

To conclude, China has firmly established itself as the world's second space power, with cutting-edge advancements across human spaceflight, space exploration, and military space capabilities. India, still a rising space power with a distinct scale of operations, has showcased technological prowess and strategic ambition, establishing itself as a significant actor in space. Their rise signals a fundamental shift in the global space order, where non-Western actors are playing an increasingly decisive role. As China continues its rapid ascent and India strengthens its position, their space programs will shape the future of space security, commercial space activities, and global space governance. Understanding their roles is essential for moving beyond a Western-centric view of space and recognizing the complex dynamics of contemporary space security.

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